

The Category of Suppositive Tense in French

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Abstract. *This article is about the category of suppositive tense in french. We know that phraseological units (hereinafter FB) are distinguished from other linguistic units by their communicative nature. According to A.G.Nazaryan, French FBs are divided into non-communicating and communicative types, and according to the words of M. Peckman, all FBs of the language are divided into word equivalent and sentence equivalent. units (word units and sentence units) can be separated.*

Key words: *language, communicative, system, the speech, the factor, personal benefits, phraseology, impersonal expressions.*

INTRODUCTION

The pragmatic characteristics of linguistic activity specific to certain linguistic units are necessarily linked to the study of the factors that cause them, and this activity is important in determining the social nature of these linguistic units. This makes it possible to find evidence confirming the achievement of language communication in accordance with social and psycho-psychological laws and therefore the development of the language system.

The starting point for the development of the language system begins with pragmatics. After all, language always serves the desires and personal benefits of the speaker. Thus, in this section, we wish to analyze some specificities of the impersonal phraseological units of French phraseology and reflect on their linguo-pragmatic specificities.

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On this basis, it is necessary to interpret FBs with impersonal expressions in French as the second type of classifications given, i.e. as communicative FBs or sentence equivalents. After all, all impersonal sentences in the French language are considered a unit equal to a sentence and reflect the communicative characteristic. Moreover, the fact that the verb in them is always in the third person singular is proof of our opinion. For example: It's a good time to arrive! - That's it, muddao! There is time for everything. - Everything in its time.

METHODS AND ANALISYS

In these examples, the presence of the verbs être and avoir in the impersonal formulas Il est, which expresses the time, and Il ya, which expresses the meaning of possession, indicates that all impersonal FBs in French are communicative FBs with the same sentence structure. There are no non-

communicating FBs, that is to say equivalent to words. They can be studied by dividing them into two types from a structural point of view in research based on collected concrete examples. In other words, it is appropriate to study FBs with impersonal sentences in French in closed and open structured FBs.

In this case, closed-structure FBs have complete meaning and end with a period, like a structurally complete sentence. Open-structured FBs, on the other hand, do not make complete sense and end with three points. For example, closed impersonal expressions: There is no smoke without fire. - If there is no wind, the tip of the tree does not move. There is a time for everything.-There is a time for everything, express impersonal expressions: It's better to... - It's better, ... It's good... - ... it's good (good) to do. Closed structure forms of these types of FB are common in French phraseology, which mainly include adverbs. Open-structured FBs, on the other hand, contain more materials.

The areas of use of French impersonal expressions in speech are quite extensive and can be classified as follows:

- in the sense of “exist” (category of existence): There is;
- in the sense of “to be” (category of necessity): It is necessary;
- in the sense of “time” (spatial category): It does;
- in the sense of “time” (category of time): It is;

There are ..., which are considered the main element of phraseological expressions in this classification Il Faut...; He does...; He is...; as derived from the content of the expression. But when used together with other components and form a phraseological phrase, they can represent other categories of meaning based on the expressed phraseological meaning features, and each of them creates speech content different from its own logic, that is to say, There is a beginning to everything.

Let's take the sentence until the gypsy walks through a door. In terms of literal translation, since it begins with the phrase There is, it reflects the meaning of existence. However, their phraseological meaning reflects the process of a certain action, denying the meaning of existence.

That is to say, it is known that the expression "Gypsy passes through a door" expresses the notion of time. Similar impersonal expressions include: They are:

Français exemples:	Impersonnel le sens de la phrase	Ouzbek interprétation:	Sens phraséologique
<i><u>Il ne faut pas ven dre la peau de l'ours avant de l'avoir tué.</u></i>	nécessité	<i>Ne pas dépoussiérer avant le troupeau.</i>	Temps
<i>Il n'y a plus que du courage.</i>	il y a	<i>Beaucoup sont partis et peu sont restés.</i>	Temps
<i><u>Il faut savoir hurler avec les loups.</u></i>	nécessité	<i>Si le temps ne se soucie pas de vous, vous vous souciez du temps.</i>	Temps
<i>Il est beau temps d'arriver !</i>	temps	<i>C'est ça , muddao !</i>	Temps

Among their main components, two types of structure can be found. This situation is linked to their forms of expression of negative meaning. Among these impersonal expressions, it is appropriate to include only Il ya meaning “to be” and It must mean “to be”. After all, cases of other impersonal expressions expressing negative meaning in FB are very rare.

CONCLUSION

At the same time, it is not enough for the discourse structure to have a grammatical form for it to become a unit of communication and find its place in the text. This structure must correspond to the text and meet the need to achieve a common communication objective. To use such expressions in the communication process, the speaker must be able to use them correctly to achieve his or her

communicative goal. Only then can it attract the listener. In the same way, the listener-recipient understands the content of the speech act, logically perceives conventional signs and can reveal their mysterious and hidden meanings only when he is familiar with the methods and means of grammaticalization [1,246].

As mentioned above, the specificities of FBs with impersonal expressions in the French language are diverse, and this approach to their study makes it possible to reveal numerous semantic, grammatical, lexical and functional specificities which are specific to them.

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